

CONNECTING EUROPE AND ASIA: SILK ROAD AND EURASIA THROUGH DUNHUANG ARTS

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Abstract

The Silk Road has always played a pivotal role in connecting more than 50 countries across its vast network spanning from one end to the other throughout history. It was not merely a conduit for caravans and trade but served as a nexus for the exchange of cultural, religious, and philosophical ideas that enriched humanity for centuries. Reviving this ancient trade route has become a contemporary topic of discussion among global leaders. Today's modern Silk Road initiatives should be regarded as bridges connecting European and Asian civilizations, fulfilling the same purpose as their historic counterpart.

This paper elucidates the intricate processes involved in the visualization, vocalization and historicization of Dunhuang's performing art traditions in both classical and modern contexts. It delves into the thorough efforts to resurrect and stage these multifaceted artistic expressions by meticulously reconstructing choreographies, musical scores, lyrics, and narratives from fragmentary archeological evidence. Simultaneously, it explores how contemporary practitioners reinterpret and innovate upon these historical blueprints to forge novel artistic forms resonating with present-day sensibilities.

By spotlighting the expressive arts of Dunhuang as a dynamic embodiment of the rich cross-cultural pollination catalyzed by the Silk Road, this research brings into vivid focus the symbiotic intermingling of aesthetic modes that reverberated across the Eurasian realm over millennia. It underscores how the flourishing of art and culture was propelled by a multidirectional circulation of customs, motifs and conventions coursing along these ancient trans-continental conduits of exchange.

Keywords: Eurasia, Silk Road, UNESCO Mogao Caves, cultural exchanges, Dunhuang expressive arts.

1. INTRODUCTION

The ancient Silk Road formed an intercontinental network connecting Europe and Asia, facilitating a vibrant exchange of goods, ideas, and cultural traditions across the Eurasian region. One of the most renowned UNESCO heritage sites situated along this fabled trade route is the city of Dunhuang in northwest China. Through extensive fieldwork carried out at Dunhuang and China's northwest regions, this paper aims to shed light on the cultural interchanges that occurred throughout the Eurasian realm by showcasing the rich tradition of expressive arts that flourished in this pivotal oasis town.

The sources for Dunhuang's music and dance genres can be traced back to a wealth of images, narratives, and musical scores unearthed from the celebrated Mogao Grottoes – a vast complex of Buddhist cave

sanctuaries designated as a UNESCO World Heritage site. While the artistic creations from the Sui (581-618 CE) and Tang (618-907 CE) dynasties form the primary wellspring for these performative traditions, they also bear the unmistakable imprint of much earlier Han dynasty (206 BCE-220 CE) aesthetics. Additionally, these traditions incorporate folkloric themes drawn from contemporaneous popular tales and secular literature.

Ideas, innovations, technologies, and creative expressions readily disseminated across the interconnected nodes of the vast Silk Road network in a multidirectional flow of cultural transmission. This exciting interchange has a profound impact on the cultures and societies dispersed around the globe. The expressive arts of Dunhuang vividly illustrate how the cross-fertilization of diverse aesthetic sensibilities converged at vital hubs like this desert outpost, catalyzing unique creative fusions.

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In March 2013, Chinese president Xi Jinping introduced the initiatives "Silk Road Economic Belt" and "21st Century Maritime Silk Road." These initiatives are now referred to as "One Belt, One Road" or the "Belt and Road Initiative". The China State Council lists in details the policies and implementation plan for this initiative on its official web page.

Scholars such as Sadik Ridvan Karluk, Suleyman Cem Karaman (2014) and Zan (2016) have noted the rise of Turkey as a regional power located in Eurasia with an extremely geopolitical position and thus plays an important role in the "Belt and Road Initiative". When examining the sociocultural and economic exchanges in Eurasia, it is critical to understand Turkey's presence in the Silk Road history. Turkey is considered as a traditional channel of the Silk Road, in which Istanbul is the end; there are a lot of ancient Silk Road remnants in the territory of Turkey. Turkey has a close relationship with the traditional Silk Road. The influence of Turkey connecting Europe and Asia is achieved through the promotion of its soft power, and the links in race, language, culture, and religion are widely utilized. In modern day Eurasian history, Turkey's secular democratic politics and market economy as a model used to have a certain appeal for many Central Asian countries.

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2. THE UNESCO DUNHUANG MOGAO CAVES

2.1. Dunhuang

Historically a frontier metropolis, Dunhuang is located at the western end of the Hexi Corridor in China's northwestern region. The Sinitic name of the geographic location Dunhuang first appeared in the *Collective Biographies of Dayuan* by Sima Qian (circa 145–86? B.C.E.) in the *Shiji* (*Records of the Grand Scribe*), which documented the diplomatic mission of Zhang Qian (d. 114 B.C.E.), a Chinese envoy twice dispatched by the Han emperor Wudi (141 B.C.–89 B.C.E.) to the Western Regions between 139 and 125 B.C.E. This mission played an important role in the opening of the Silk Roads, which linked the Mediterranean coast with central China and beyond via oasis towns such as Samarkand.

Travelers, especially Buddhist monks from India and central Asia, passing through Dunhuang on their way to Chang'an (present day Xi'an), China's ancient capital, would stop to meditate in the Mogao Caves and consult manuscripts in the monastery's library.

At the same time, Chinese pilgrims would travel by foot from China through central Asia to Pakistan, India, Nepal, Bangladesh, and Sri Lanka, playing a key role in the exchanges between ancient China and the outside world. Travelers from China would stop to acquire provisions at Dunhuang before crossing the Gobi Desert to continue their long journey abroad.

Dunhuang became a strategic site along the Silk Road in northwestern China, a crossroads of trade, and a

locus for religious, cultural, and intellectual influences since the Han dynasty (206 B.C.E.–220 C.E.). (Kuang 2016).

2.1.1 Mogao Caves

Commonly known as Thousand Buddha caves, the caves at the Mogao cliff near the modern town of Dunhuang have served as temples, sites for performative events, and an archive that consisted of medieval Chinese paintings and Buddhist sutras. (Fig. 1) Among the 735 caves, there are 492 caves with murals, the mural area is about 45,000 square meters.

Fig. 1. Landmark stone on the ground at the UNESCO Dunhuang Mogao Grottoes in Gansu Province, China. Photo credit: Lanlan Kuang, 2023.

The Dunhuang Academy was founded in 1943 to protect and study the Dunhuang relics, and the Mogao Grottoes were included in the first list of National Cultural Relics established by the Chinese government, in 1961. In 1987, when reform was one of the most common words in China's sociopolitical vocabulary, China's post-Mao leaders began to reformulate their foreign policies and their involvement in United Nations cultural programs (Shichor 1991).

The Dunhuang Academy is now responsible for preservation of the site. (Fig.2) To this end, many domestic and international organizations, including the Getty Conservation Institute have collaborated with the Academy. The Dunhuang Academy has posted panoramas of their preservation work. The Getty Institute in the United States also housed a 3D, panoramic replica of Cave 45 that surprisingly was not turned into a traveling exhibit, thus limiting the visibility of the project and the caves.

Fig. 2. Moago Cave No. 96, the nine-story building housing the 35.5 high Maitreya Buddha statue constructed during the Tang dynasty, in 695 under the edicts from Empress Wu Zetian. The caves are managed by Dunhuang Academy. Photo credit: Lanlan Kuang, 2023.

Today, the Dunhuang Mogao Caves is among one of the most well-known UNESCO heritage sites along the ancient Silk Road. With a history of more than 1600 years, it is the largest and most abundant Buddhist art place in the world.

3. DUNHUANG MURAL AND DUNHUANG DANCE

3.1. Dunhuang Mural and Dunhuang Dance

In the case of the Dunhuang mural music and dance genre, as noted earlier, the sources of the genre are primarily images, narratives, and musical tunes depicted in the wall paintings and/or documents discovered in the Dunhuang Mogao Grottoes. The genre tends to draw mainly from the artistic creations from the Sui (581–618) and Tang (618–907) dynasties, although artistic patterns established earlier, beginning in the Han dynasty (206 B.C.E.–220 C.E.) are also evident, as are folkloric motifs from contemporary popular narratives and vernacular literature with nonreligious themes. A perfect example would be the “Lotus Aloft” dance drama discuss below; it was built on a Chinese folklorized Buddhist story.

3.1.1 Dunhuang Murals

Floral, animal, and other patterns have been used to decorate the inner surfaces of the cave at Dunhuang. They are unusually depicted on the ceiling or the borders of different pictures. The lotus flower, or perhaps we should say, the various kinds of lotus pattern decorated in the Dunhuang Mogao caves are exquisite and highly representational. Although their main function is ornamental, most patterns have their own symbolic meanings.

Scholars have divided the lotus pattern into several categories: the round-wheel lotus pattern appeared in the Northern dynasties (397-581 AD) as decorative pattern, the simple yet geometrically sophisticated flat-petal lotus from the Sui and Tang dynasties (581-907 AD) that are seen often with three rabbit patterns, the curl petal lotus appeared in the middle Tang Dynasty (782-847 AD) and continued to be used in Five Dynasties (907-979 AD), and the peach-shaped lotus from the early Tang Dynasty (618-712 AD) which evolved into the Baoxiang flower pattern during the mid or the high Tang Dynasty (650-755 AD). An imaginary floral pattern, or floral semiotic, Baoxiang flower is not a flower that can be seen in nature. It gathers the character of the lotus pattern of India, the honeysuckle pattern of the Western Region, the peony pattern and the pomegranate patterns, curl petal lotus, and Baoxiang flower.

This popular Tang decorative pattern could be seen in Cave 331 in the center of the caisson. Lotus lower symbolizes purity and the Buddhist law while the Baoxiang Flower (a combination of peony and other lowers) stands for majesty and beauty. The Sui dynasty cave 407 is best known of all the three-hares designs at Dunhuang. The hares are surrounded by two bands of lotus petals against a background of celestial maidens (*feitian*) flying in the same direction as the hares.

3.1.2 Dunhuang dance

The Dunhuang dance known to us today is a multifaceted genre of music, dance, and theatrical performances that was created in the twentieth century and based primarily on artifact excavated from China's northwestern frontier metropolis, Dunhuang.

Studies on the Dunhuang dance could be approached in numerous ways. Kinesthetics semiotics, the study of signs through bodily movement, for instance, is one that often used by dance researchers. In the field of dance, signs in a dance production appear in the form of choreographic elements such as theme, movement, gesture, facial expression, proxemics (the use of space), costume, props, and technological elements such as lighting, sound, and setting. A staged dance is the product of cultural agreement, the result of a systematic use of various choreographic codes and conventions.

A perfect example would be the “Lotus Aloft” dance drama, which was built on a Chinese folklorized Buddhist story. The term “Lotus Aloft” is the English translation of a Chinese idiom which enacts the figurative symbolic motivation of lotus flower in association to Buddhism. It may be traced to the fifth-century *Za baozang jing* (Scripture on the Storehouse of Sundry Treasures, T. 203), which contains the story of Lady Deer manifesting a lotus flower on each step she took. Representing beauty, purity, and youthfulness, the lotus flower is in Buddhism a floral semiotic symbol denoting the essence of enlightenment of those who have meditated and will meditate on the profound Law. The lotus supports the Buddha as the flower supports the world above the chaotic waters of the universe. Its virtues and characteristics can be revealed from creative poetic metaphors and phraseological units, whose figurative components reflect its cultural symbolism.

4. CONCLUSION

In 2019 and 2020, China's Lanzhou Song & Dance Theatre continues their world tour of the award-winning *Dunhuang, My Dream* theatrical dance drama at the home of the New York Ballet, the David H. Koch Theater, in Lincoln Center.

The creation of the Dunhuang mural dance may be perceived beyond an embodied re-interpretation of the narratives on the Dunhuang Mogao Grottoes, one of the most well-known UNESCO heritages on the Silk Road. The Silk Road expressive arts are the sociocultural phenomena that emerges through interactions and negotiations among multiple actors and institutions to envision and enact contemporary cultural exchanges among civilizations along the Silk Road. Connecting Europe and Asia, such phenomena are arguably involved in the re-creation of historical memory and identity of countries with rich cultures in the Eurasian region in contemporary moments of contestation and transformation.

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